

Existence and uniqueness for a fractional differential equation involving Atangana-Baleanu derivative by using a new contraction

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Abstract

In this study, by using some new contractions, we obtain an existence and uniqueness conclusion for a fractional differential equation with Atangana-Baleanu derivative as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}({}_0^{ABC}D^\kappa \delta)(s) &= h(s, \delta(s)), & s \in J, 0 \leq \kappa \leq 1, \\ \delta(0) &= \delta_0,\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where D^ς is the Atangana-Baleanu derivative of order ς and f is continuous with $f(0, h(0)) = 0$.

Keywords: Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative, orbitally complete, fixed point.

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1. Introduction

Fractional calculus is a part of mathematical analysis that studies the performance of derivative and integral operations on non integer orders. In the past years, early works in fractional calculus were limited to mathematics.

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Recently, this field had found many applications in various directions such as applied mathematics, electrochemistry, tracer in fluid flows, fractional-order multi-poles in electromagnetism, finance, signal processing, bio-engineering, viscoelasticity, fluid mechanics, and fluid dynamics [16].

Definitions of two famous fractional derivatives, namely Riemann-Liouville and Caputo, included a singular kernel. Recently Caputo and Fabrizio provided a definition with a nonsingular kernel which the properties of this new definition can be found in [14].

In 2016, the interesting and new derivatives without singular kernel were introduced by Atangana and Baleanu, which generalized the Caputo-Fabrizio definition [7]. Atangana-Baleanu derivative contains Mittag-Leffler function as a nonlocal and nonsingular kernel. Recently, Atangana et al. provided the numerical approximation to the fractional advection-diffusion equation whose fractional derivatives are Atangana-Baleanu derivative of Riemann-Liouville type [11].

One of the efficient methods in investigating the existence and uniqueness of the solutions of differential equations is using of fixed point theory and for this reason there is a long history of presenting various fixed point theorems (see [1]-[12]).

In [6], Bryant proposed a relaxation of the Banach contractive condition involving the iteration of the function. Recall that, for a positive integer n we denote by h^n the n^{th} iterate of h , so that $u_0 = h^0u$ and $h^{n+1}u = h(h^nu)$ for $u \in X$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Hereupon, the tripled (X, d, h) represent a metric space (X, d) with a self-mapping h on it. We shall use (X^*, d, h) to indicate the corresponding metric space is complete. Shatanawi and Karapinar in [9] introduced F_S -contractions in the sense of Wardowski and Seghal and F_J -contractions in the sense of Wardowski and Jachymski. Then, they ensured some existence and uniqueness fixed point results.

In this work, by using some contractions of mentioned results in [9], we obtain an existence and uniqueness conclusion for a fractional differential equation with Atangana-Baleanu derivative as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} ({}^ABC D^\kappa \delta)(s) &= h(s, \delta(s)), & s \in J, 0 \leq \kappa \leq 1, \\ \delta(0) &= \delta_0, \end{aligned} \tag{1.1}$$

where D^ς is the Atangana-Baleanu derivative of order ς and f is continuous with $f(0, h(0)) = 0$. Also, Throughout the article \mathfrak{J} denote $[0, 1]$.

Now, here is the following fixed point theorem.

Definition 1.1. [10] Let $\delta \in H^1(a, b)$, $a < b$ and $0 \leq \kappa \leq 1$. The Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative in Caputo sense of δ of order κ is defined by

$$({}^ABC D^\kappa \delta)(s) = \frac{B(\kappa)}{1 - \kappa} \int_a^s \delta'(\nu) E_\kappa \left[-\kappa \frac{(s - \nu)^\kappa}{1 - \kappa} \right] d\nu, \tag{1.2}$$

where E_κ is the Mittag-Leffler function defined by $E_\kappa(z) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(n\kappa+1)}$ and $B(\kappa)$ is a normalizing positive function satisfying $B(0) = B(1) = 1$ (see [? 13]). The associated fractional integral is defined by

$$({}^AB I^\kappa \delta)(s) = \frac{1 - \kappa}{\kappa} \delta(s) + \frac{\kappa}{B(\kappa)} ({}_a I^\kappa \delta)(s), \tag{1.3}$$

where ${}_a I^\kappa$ is the left Riemann-Liouville fractional integral given as

$$({}_a I^\kappa \delta)(s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \int_a^s (s - \nu)^{\kappa-1} \delta(\nu) d\nu. \tag{1.4}$$

Consider $d : M \times M \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ given by

$$d(\delta, \sigma) = \| (\delta - \sigma)^2 \|_\infty = \sup_{s \in J} (\delta(s) - \sigma(s))^2,$$

where $M = C(J, \mathbb{R})$ denote the set of continuous functions, (M, d) is a complete b -metric space with $s_1 = 2$. We discuss about problem

$$\begin{aligned} ({}^0_{ABC} D^\kappa \delta)(s) &= h(s, \delta(s)), & s \in J, 0 \leq \kappa \leq 1, \\ \delta(0) &= \delta_0, \end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

where D^κ is the Atangana-Baleanu derivative in Caputo sense of order κ and $h : J \times M \rightarrow M$ is continuous with $h(0, \delta(0)) = 0$.

Proposition 1.2. [5] For $0 < \kappa < 1$, we have

$$({}^{AB} I_b^{\kappa ABC} D^\kappa \delta)(s) = \delta(s) - \delta(b). \tag{1.6}$$

2. Main results

For a positive integer n we denote by h^n the n th iterate of h , so that $y = h^0 y$ and $h^{n+1} y = h(h^n y)$ for $y \in X$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The tripled (X, d, h) represent a metric space (X, d) with a self-mapping h on it. We shall use (X^*, d, h) to indicate the corresponding metric space is complete. Also on (X, d, h) an orbit of $y_0 \in X$ is the set

$$O(y_0) = \{h^n y_0 : n = 0, 1, 2, \dots\},$$

and $\rho(y_0)$ denote to the diameter of the set $O(y_0)$. Note that for any subset B of X , $\rho(B) = \sup\{d(u, y) : u, y \in B\}$ is the diameter of B . We shall use the tripled (X_{0^*}, d, h) if for some $y \in X$, every Cauchy sequence from $O(y)$ converges in X . In this case, the corresponding space is called orbitally complete.

Corollary 2.1. [9] For (X, d^*, h) with $p : X \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, we suppose there exists $\tau > 0$ such that for $v, w \in X$

$$d(h^{p(y)} y, h^{p(y)} w) \leq e^{-\tau} d(y, w). \tag{2.1}$$

Assume there exists $y_0 \in X$ such that $0 < \rho < \infty$. Moreover, (X, d) is h -orbitally complete. Then h has a unique fixed point.

Theorem 2.2. Suppose for the problem given (1.5), we have the following:

$$|h(p, \delta(p)) - h(p, \sigma(p))| \leq \frac{B(\xi)\Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi)+1} e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right|, \quad p \in J,$$

and

$$|h(p, \delta(p))| + |h(p, \sigma(p))| \leq \frac{B(\xi)\Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi)+1} e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right|, \quad p \in J, \tau > 0.$$

Then the problem (1.5) has a unique solution.

Proof. Considering $d : M \times M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$, define a metric d as follows: $d(\delta, \sigma) = \sup_{p \in J} |\delta(p) - \sigma(p)|$. Applying the Atangana-Baleanu integral and using Proposition 1.2, we have

$$(T\delta)(p) = \delta_0 + {}^0_{AB} I^\xi h(p, \delta(p)).$$

We show that the equation (1.5) has a unique solution.

$$\begin{aligned}
 |T\delta(p) - T\sigma(p)| &= \left| {}^{AB}I^\xi [h(p, \delta(p)) - h(p, \sigma(p))] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{1-\xi}{B(\xi)} |h(p, \delta(p)) - h(p, \sigma(p))| \\
 &\quad + \frac{\xi}{B(\xi)} {}_0I^\xi |h(p, \delta(p)) - h(p, \sigma(p))| \\
 &\leq \frac{1-\xi}{B(\xi)} \cdot \frac{B(\xi) \cdot \Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi) + 1} e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \\
 &\quad + \frac{\xi}{B(\xi)} \cdot \frac{B(\xi) \cdot \Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi) + 1} {}_0I^\xi(1) e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \\
 &= \left(\frac{B(\xi) \cdot \Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi) + 1} e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \right) \times \left(\frac{1-\xi}{B(\xi)} + \frac{\xi}{B(\xi)} \cdot \frac{1}{\xi \cdot \Gamma(\xi)} \right) \\
 &\leq e^{-\tau} \sup \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |T\delta(p)| + |T\sigma(p)| &= \left| {}^{AB}I^\xi [h(p, \delta(p))] \right| + \left| {}^{AB}I^\xi [h(p, \sigma(p))] \right| \\
 &\leq {}^{AB}I^\xi [|h(p, \delta(p))| + |h(p, \sigma(p))|] \\
 &\leq \frac{1-\xi}{B(\xi)} \cdot \frac{B(\xi) \cdot \Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi) + 1} e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \\
 &\quad + \frac{\xi}{B(\xi)} \cdot \frac{B(\xi) \cdot \Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi) + 1} {}_0I^\xi(1) e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \\
 &= \left(\frac{B(\xi) \cdot \Gamma(\xi)}{(1-\xi)\Gamma(\xi) + 1} e^{-\tau} \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \right) \times \left(\frac{1-\xi}{B(\xi)} + \frac{\xi}{B(\xi)} \cdot \frac{1}{\xi \cdot \Gamma(\xi)} \right) \\
 &\leq e^{-\tau} \sup \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right| \leq \sup \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right|
 \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$[\sup (|T\delta(p)| + |T\sigma(p)|)] \leq \sup \left| \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|} \right|$$

Also we have the following relation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(T^2\delta, T^2\sigma) &= \sup(|T^2\delta(p) - T^2\sigma(p)|) \\
 &= \sup(|T\delta(p) - T\sigma(p)|) \times \sup(|T\delta(p) + T\sigma(p)|) \\
 &\leq \sup(|T\delta(p) - T\sigma(p)|) \times \sup(|T\delta(p)| + |T\sigma(p)|) \\
 &\leq e^{-\tau} (\sup \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} - \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|}) \times (\sup \sqrt{|\delta(p)|} + \sqrt{|\sigma(p)|}) \\
 &= e^{-\tau} \sup ||\delta(p)| - |\sigma(p)|| \\
 &\leq e^{-\tau} \sup |\delta(p) - \sigma(p)| \\
 &= e^{-\tau} d(\delta, \sigma).
 \end{aligned}$$

So, the condition (2.1) for $p : X \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, $p(\delta) = 2$ and $\delta \in M$ is true. Hence by Corollary 2, the problem (1.5), has a unique solution. □

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